

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Mugharet el'Aliya: Affinities of an enigmatic north African Aterian maxillary fragment

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Abstract

Objectives: This study uses a virtual framework to examine the left maxillary fragment of the juvenile fossil from Mugharet el'Aliya, Morocco, found in association with an Aterian lithic industry. Previously, this fossil had been ascribed to modern humans or the Neanderthal lineage based on its “archaic”/“Neanderthal-like” features and apparent large size. Here, we conducted a novel 3D shape comparative analysis of the maxillary fragment to clarify its taxonomic affinities with regard to its size and ontogeny.

Materials and Methods: Eighty Computed Tomography and surface scans representing ontogenetic samples of *Homo sapiens* and *Homo neanderthalensis* were used to capture species-specific differences. The toolkit of geometric morphometrics in combination with surface registration and an elastic iterative closest point algorithm were used to create a dataset of meshes with an identical number of corresponding vertices for the maxillae. Multivariate statistics were applied to Procrustes superimposed coordinates derived from the vertices of this dataset.

Results: Our analysis showed affinities of the Mugharet el'Aliya individual with our *H. sapiens* sample, especially with a subadult individual from Qafzeh. No size-independent affinities with Neanderthals of comparable dental age could be identified.

Discussion: Our results add to the evidence connecting fossils from western Asia, especially Qafzeh and Skhul, and the North African Aterian. Furthermore, Mugharet el'Aliya adds to our knowledge of the ontogenetic development of adult morphology that is frequently used to characterize hominin groups, for example, Neanderthals and modern humans.

KEYWORDS

Aterian, Mugharet el'Aliya, Neanderthal affinities, ontogeny, surface registration

1 | INTRODUCTION

North Africa, long considered a peripheral geographical region in comparison with eastern or southern Africa (e.g., Balter, 2011), has

recently gained renewed importance in modern human origins research. Resumed work at the site of Jebel Irhoud, Morocco, pushed back the appearance of *Homo sapiens* remains associated with an early Middle Stone Age (MSA) to ca. 300 ka (Hublin

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et al., 2017; Richter et al., 2017), the earliest date known for our lineage. This discovery contributed greatly to the formulation of the pan-African model for modern human origins (e.g., review in Henn et al., 2018; references therein) and highlights the complexity of the evolutionary processes that led to the appearance of our lineage.

The later Moroccan human fossil record, including fossils associated with the Aterian lithic industry, has garnered less attention despite its relevance to modern human evolution. While some researchers have considered Aterian fossils to represent the oldest anatomically modern humans in Northern Africa (Hublin, 1993; references therein), their geological age, and therefore relevance to human origins, has been unclear. Redating of Aterian sites points to an earlier and longer chronology than previously considered ranging from ca. 145–20 ka, and thereby, to a possible overlap with a lithic industry attributed to the early MSA (historically referred to as “African Mousterian”) during MIS5-6, underlining the potential evolutionary significance of these remains (e.g., Barton et al., 2009; Doerschner et al., 2016; Hublin et al., 2012; Jacobs et al., 2011; Mercier et al., 2007; Richter et al., 2010, 2012). Human fossils associated with the Aterian industry remain poorly understood, being described as showing a mixture of primitive and derived traits with robust jaws and high levels of megadonty, particularly in the post-canine dentition (e.g., Ferembach, 1976; Hublin et al., 2012; Hublin & Tillier, 1981; Smith et al., 2007). Especially during the first half of the 20th century, this combination of features often led to the attribution of such fossils (e.g., McBurney et al., 1953; Şenyürek, 1940)—as well as the specimens from Jebel Irhoud (Ennouchi, 1962)—to the Neanderthal lineage. Although these are now generally recognized as early *H. sapiens* with some similarities to individuals from Skhul and Qafzeh, Israel (e.g., Freidline et al., 2021; Harvati & Hublin, 2012; Hublin et al., 2012; Hublin & Tillier, 1988), the origin of their archaic morphology remains unclear and is an important topic of investigation for understanding evolutionary processes underlying modern human origins in the region. This is especially true in light of paleogenetic evidence of repeated interbreeding among human lineages, both in Eurasia and in Africa, in the Pleistocene (e.g., Dannemann & Racimo, 2018; Durvasula & Sankararaman, 2020; Hsieh et al., 2016; Lachance et al., 2012; Meyer et al., 2016; Posth et al., 2017); of fossil evidence pointing to considerable geographic dispersals of early human populations (Harvati et al., 2019; Hershkovitz et al., 2018); and of the geographic position of North Africa at the southern rim of the Mediterranean Basin as a potential dispersal corridor and contact zone for early human groups (e.g., Bae et al., 2017; Green et al., 2010; Lazaridis et al., 2016; Osborne et al., 2008; Prüfer et al., 2014). It is increasingly clear that the origin of *H. sapiens* was a more complicated process than previously thought, and the Aterian human fossil record can help shed light on this complexity.

Here, we aim to contribute to this discussion by examining the fragmentary left maxilla from Mugharet el'Aliya in the framework of virtual anthropology. Our goal is to help clarify the phylogenetic and taxonomic affinities of this enigmatic specimen and to analyze its archaic, “Neanderthal-like” features in the context of size and ontogeny.

1.1 | Mugharet el'Aliya: Background and previous studies

A left maxillary fragment of a juvenile hominin with three unerupted teeth (see below) was recovered in 1939 from the cave site of Mugharet el'Aliya (Coon in Şenyürek, 1940). The site is part of the Caves of Hercules, a cave complex on the Moroccan Atlantic coast at Cap Ashakar, now located 18 m above sea level (35°45'N, 5°56'W; Wrinn & Rink, 2003). It was known at the time for yielding archeological material mainly attributed to the Neolithic and Later Stone Age (LSA) (Bouzouggar et al., 2002). Layers underlying the LSA were first excavated in 1939 and ascribed to the Aterian period (Bouzouggar et al., 2002; Coon, 1957a). The maxillary fragment was presumably recovered during sieving of unmixed sand from the lowest and oldest layer that had yielded the Aterian tools (Coon in Bouzouggar et al., 2002; Coon, 1957a; Howe, 1967; Şenyürek, 1940; Wrinn & Rink, 2003). The cave is now almost completely emptied of its sediments, preventing the assessment of the exact provenance of the fossil, whose geological age, therefore, remains uncertain (Bouzouggar et al., 2002; Wrinn & Rink, 2003). The original provenance of the fossil reported by Coon was later questioned, suggesting that the discovery was a surface find within a trench (Coon, 1957b). Moreover, fluorine analyses performed using samples extracted from the maxilla did not match the dates of the layer originally associated with the fossil (Coon, 1957b; Minugh-Purvis, 1993). Dating of faunal remains showed Aterian occupations between 35 and 60 ka at Mugharet el'Aliya (Wrinn & Rink, 2003), thus providing a broad chronological framework. Because the sediment layers that purportedly yielded the maxilla include both the youngest and oldest Aterian layers, its age cannot be constrained beyond this period. In addition to the maxillary fragment, an isolated permanent second molar was recovered in 1939 (Şenyürek, 1940) and two additional teeth were reported in 1947, which remain undescribed (Hublin, 1993). The presence of at least two fossil individuals at Mugharet el'Aliya is indicated by the combination of heavy dental wear on the permanent molar and subadult status of the maxillary fragment (Şenyürek, 1940).

1.2 | Mugharet el'Aliya maxilla

The maxillary fragment was originally described by Şenyürek (1940). The unerupted left upper third premolar and left upper canine were removed after the initial description by opening the crypts using a dentist's drill (Şenyürek, 1940). Moreover, samples for fluorine and nitrogen analysis were removed from the maxilla (although the location of the samples collected was not recorded) and the anterior nasal spine was damaged at some point after the excavation (Minugh-Purvis, 1993). As a result, details of the original anatomy of the fossil have been altered or lost.

The fragment comprises the left maxilla from approximately the midline to the anterior border of the crypt of the permanent second molar and includes the almost complete zygomatic process, left nasal

FIGURE 1 Virtual reconstruction of the left maxillary fragment of Mugharet el'Aliya. Shown in (a) anterior, (b) antero-lateral, (c) lateral, (d) posterior, (e) medial, (f) superior and (g) inferior view. Mugharet el'Aliya is courtesy of the Peabody Museum of Archaeology and Ethnology, Harvard University, 39-69-50/N3635.0.

opening, and facies frontalis inferior to the infraorbital foramen (Figure 1; Minugh-Purvis, 1993; Şenyürek, 1940). Based on the dental developmental status, this juvenile individual is considered to have been ca. 9 years old at the time of death, with an age range of ± 2 years (Minugh-Purvis, 1993; Şenyürek, 1940). The maxilla is large in absolute size and has thick bone walls (Şenyürek, 1940). The preserved external anatomy lacks a deep and distinct canine fossa, and the root of the zygomatic process is placed anterior to the first permanent molar, originating at the deciduous second molar (Minugh-Purvis, 1993; Şenyürek, 1940). These two features deviate from the typical adult modern human maxillary anatomy, whose ontogenetic manifestation remains in part elusive (cf. e.g., Minugh-Purvis, 1993; Lieberman et al., 2002; Schuh et al., 2020). Additionally, several modern human traits are not clearly identified in the Mugharet el'Aliya maxilla, including an angle of about 90° between the anterior surface of the zygomatic bone to the midline, the inferior border of the zygoma being either vertically below the superior border or being retracted, and the inferior border of the zygomatic margin (IZM; also called zygomaticoalveolar crest) reaching the alveolar process in a sharp inflection with a malar notch (e.g., Lacruz et al., 2019; Pope, 1991). However, a clear presence of an “*incurvatio inframalaris frontalis*” along the transverse plane of the Mugharet el'Aliya maxilla was reported (Hublin, 1993, 2000; Minugh-Purvis, 1993). A curvature at the IZM and the “*incurvatio inframalaris frontalis*” are considered to be marked features in modern humans and weak or absent in Neanderthals (e.g., Lacruz et al., 2019; Pope, 1991; Sergi, 1947; Weber & Krenn, 2017). In all, the preserved anatomy of the Mugharet el'Aliya maxilla has been described as showing modern human-like, unclear, or “archaic”/“Neanderthal-like” features.

2 | MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 | Sample

We evaluated the external morphology of the maxillary fragment through a set of 80 CT and surface scans (Table 1; Table S1). Individuals from the comparative sample were assigned to one of three groups: Neanderthals (Roc the Marsal, Pech de l'Azé, La Quina H18, Teshik Tash, Amud, Shanidar 1, La Ferrassie 1, Forbes' Quarry 1, Saccopastore 2), later *H. sapiens* (Grotte des Enfants 6, Nazlet Khater 2, Abri Pataud, Mladec 1, Predmosti 3, Liujiang, Holocene sample), and early *H. sapiens* (Qafzeh 10, Qafzeh 6, Skhul V, Jebel Irhoud 1, Omo 1). In addition, the dataset was divided into developmental age groups (see below).

2.2 | Age estimation

Developmental age groups were based on dental eruption stages (e.g., Freidline et al., 2012; Mori & Harvati, 2019; Robson & Wood, 2008; Smith, 1989; Zihlman et al., 2004). We used the eruption status of the permanent maxillary dentition to assign each individual to one of four dental age groups: (3) complete deciduous dentition; (4) erupted first molar; (5) erupted second molar; and (6) adult with erupted third molar. Modern humans with an erupted second molar and a closed spheno-basilar synchondrosis (SBS) were treated as adults due to the highly variable eruption time of the third molar (Carter & Worthington, 2015). We did not include age groups 1 and 2, that is, individuals with no or incomplete deciduous dentition, to target comparable age groups for Mugharet el'Aliya; age group 6 was included to cover the adult interspecific variation.

TABLE 1 Sample used in the dataset. Individuals are grouped in four dental age groups (3: Complete deciduous dentition; 4: $M^1 > 3/4$ erupted; 5: $M^2 > 3/4$ erupted; 6: $M^3 > 3/4$ erupted and SBS fused)

Dental age group	Geological age groups	Country of origin	Individuals ^a	Abbreviation for fossil individuals
3	<i>Homo sapiens</i> Holocene	Tunisia	1	
		Germany	3	
		South Africa	6	
	<i>Homo neanderthalensis</i> Late Pleistocene	France	Roc de Marsal	RdM
			Pech de l'Azé	PdA
4	Late Pleistocene	Morocco	Mugharet el'Aliya	El'Aliya
		<i>Homo sapiens</i> Holocene	Tunisia	2
		Egypt	1	
		Germany	9	
		South Africa	9	
	Late Pleistocene	Israel	Qafzeh 10	QA10
	<i>Homo neanderthalensis</i> Late Pleistocene	France	La Quina H18	LQ18
		Middle/Late Pleistocene	Uzbekistan	Teshik Tash
5	<i>Homo sapiens</i> Holocene	Germany	11	
		South Africa	1	
	Late Pleistocene	Italy	Grotte des Enfants 6	GdE6
6	<i>Homo sapiens</i> Holocene	Germany	5	
		Tanzania	5	
		South Africa	6	
	Late Pleistocene	Egypt	Nazlet Khater 2	NK2
		France	Abri Pataud	AP
		Czech Republic	Mladec 1	ML1
			Predmosti 3	PR3
		China	Liujiang	LI
		Israel	Qafzeh 6	QA6
	Middle Pleistocene		Skhul V	SK5
		Morocco	Jebel Irhoud 1	IR1
		Ethiopia	Omo 1	OM1
	<i>Homo neanderthalensis</i> Late Pleistocene	Israel	Amud	AM
			Shanidar 1	SH1
		France	La Ferrassie 1	LF
Gibraltar		Forbes' Quarry 1	FQ	
		Saccopastore 2	SA2	
Middle/Late Pleistocene		Italy		

^aFor Holocene non-fossil individuals only the number of used individuals provided.

2.3 | Measurement protocol

Attempts to analyze the microanatomy of the maxilla to determine its predominant pattern of facial growth and remodeling, which has been shown to separate modern *H. sapiens* from Neanderthals (Lacruz et al., 2015), were unsuccessful due to a thick layer of preservative on the fossil. Thus, we focused our analysis on geometric morphometric methods. The Mugharet el'Aliya maxilla preserves only a limited number of diagnostic features, restricting the use of common linear measurements employed in classical comparative analyses of fossils. In

addition, insufficient homologous points and structures are preserved for a comprehensive study using the standard toolkit of geometric morphometrics, which captures shape as a configuration of landmarks. Landmarks are homologous points covering recognizable bony structures that can be extended by semi-landmarks on curves and surfaces (for discussion see e.g., Bookstein, 1997; Gunz et al., 2005; Mitteroecker & Gunz, 2009; Slice, 2007; Zelditch et al., 2012). To maximize the analysis of the preserved external morphology of Mugharet el'Aliya we followed a recently described protocol for surface registration (cf. Schlager & Rüdell, 2013; Figure 2). To our knowledge,

FIGURE 2 Visualization of the main steps for the method of surface registration. (a) Original maxillary fragment; (b) extracted external maxillary surface as single-layered triangular mesh; (c) landmark placement (see Table 2 for definitions); (d) initial landmark-based thin-plate spline registration of reference onto each target mesh; (e) elastic ICP-matching of surfaces from (d), resulting in new single-layered triangular meshes; (f) extraction of the vertices as coordinates for further analysis. Mugharet e'Aliya is courtesy of the Peabody Museum of Archaeology and Ethnology, Harvard University, 39-69-50/N3635.0.

TABLE 2 Definitions for the landmarks used in the initial step of registration

Number in Figure 2c	Landmark definition
1	Interalveolar septa between the first and second incisor (here either deciduous or permanent dentition) ^a
2	Point of maximum curvature between Alare (lateral-most point of the nasal aperture) and inferior-most margin of nasal aperture
3	Infero-medial foramen infraorbitale
4	Posterior-most point on the processus zygomaticus maxillae before the zygomaxillary suture
5	Anterior inter-alveolar septa of the first permanent molar (here either between UP ⁴ /M ¹ or dm ² /M ¹) ^a

^aDepending on dental age group as the sample includes complete deciduous, mixed and complete permanent dentition.

this study is among the first to use surface registration in a fossil context. It offers a unique opportunity for the study of the fragmentary Mugharet e'Aliya specimen, despite some shortcomings that the use of this method entails (cf. Sections 2.4 and 4).

The goal of the surface registration protocol is to deform a reference mesh to best match a target mesh by using Gaussian smoothed displacement vectors (Moshfeghi et al., 1994). By deforming the reference to match several target meshes, a sample of triangular meshes with the identical number of corresponding vertices is created. These vertices can be extracted and used as coordinates during analyses. Here, Mugharet e'Aliya was the reference and all other individuals were considered the targets.

In a first step, we extracted the external maxillary surface from each scan. For CT scans, this included semi-automated segmentation based on manual placement of a seed as starting point for an automated threshold-based segmentation followed by potential manual corrections of the segmentation. Based on the segmentation a triangular mesh was created which was transformed into a single-layered mesh of the region of interest by removing all residual vertices. Surface scans include triangular meshes as direct output. Therefore, our mesh manipulation was limited to the removal of all vertices not required for a single-layered mesh of the region of interest. The creation of single-layered triangular meshes and mesh cleaning are essential in avoiding distortions in the following steps. Extracted surfaces from the right side were mirrored to the left side and their vertex orientation was inverted. In the next step, an initial landmark-based registration between the reference and each target was carried out by using the thin-plate spline (TPS) algorithm (Figure 2c,d; Table 2; Zelditch et al., 2012). After the initial registration, an iterative closest point algorithm was used to best match the reference onto the target (also called ICP-matching). The ICP-matching was coupled with an elastic component based on Gaussian displacement vectors (Moshfeghi et al., 1994) and was run automatically with 40 iterations. Each iteration contained the four following steps (cf. Schlager & Rüdell, 2013): (1) each vertex of the reference mesh was projected onto the target mesh; (2) this was followed by discarding all displacement vectors for closest points that point to the wrong direction or where the angle between the normal and the displacement vector exceeded 45°; (3) the resulting displacement vectors were smoothed by applying Gaussian smoothing based on the neighborhood of each vertex; and (4) the resulting surface was smoothed to prevent mesh folding (Vollmer et al., 1999).

FIGURE 3 Box-Whisker plots as illustration of centroid size (CS) distribution per dental age group within the later *H. sapiens* (red), early *H. sapiens* (dark red) and Neanderthal (blue) samples as well as Mughareh el'Aliya (black). Subadult fossil individuals assigned to dental age group 3 are shown as triangles, age group 4 as squares and age group 5 as inverted triangles. Dental age groups, abbreviations, CS of all individuals and summary statistics underlying the Box-Whisker plots are listed in Table 1 and Tables S3, S4, S5, respectively

As a final step, the coordinates underlying the vertices were extracted and Generalized Procrustes analysis (GPA) was used to superimpose the coordinates of all individuals to allow a statistical analysis of the resulting Procrustes shape coordinates. During GPA, information about orientation and location is removed and the landmark configurations are scaled to centroid size (CS), calculated as the square root of the summed squared of each landmark-centroid distance (e.g., Zelditch et al., 2012).

2.4 | Error calculations

Multiple measurements of the same individual were carried out by two observers (C. R.; J. Z.). Distances between repeated measures of landmarks placed for initial registration as well as between resulting surfaces were calculated (Figures S1 and S2). Out of all vertex combinations of the error measurements ($N = 1,574,730$) less than

0.001% ($N = 51$) exceed a displacement of 1 mm, all of which were located at the edges of the meshes and can be explained by observer error during landmark placement. Additionally, the error introduced by the method itself was assessed by comparing each mesh created via surface registration with the corresponding original. For well-preserved, complete individuals distance heat maps show almost no displacement within the surface area (Figure S3a–c). For individuals with taphonomic damage or showing structures not present in the reference mesh (e.g., additional foramen), the displacement can locally exceed 1 mm and creates a smoothed mesh surface (Figure S3d–f; cf. Section 4.3). Smoothing restricted to small locally confined surface areas while preserving the vast majority of the original surface does not significantly affect the analyses (cf. Veneziano et al., 2018). However, individuals where surface registration resulted in large smoothed areas, were excluded from the sample, to avoid artifacts and potential influence on the analyses (cf. Profico et al., 2016).

FIGURE 4 Maxillary shape principal component analysis with Mughareh el'Aliya and all early *H. sapiens* fossils projected into the plot, PC1 plotted against PC2. Later *H. sapiens* shown in light red ($N = 65$), early *H. sapiens* samples in darker red ($N = 5$), and *H. neanderthalensis* in blue ($N = 9$). Individuals assigned to dental age group 3 are shown as triangles, age group 4 as squares, age group 5 as inverted triangles and age group 6 as dots. Mughareh el'Aliya is shown as a black square. Shape changes along PCs illustrated as surfaces at ± 2 sd and direct comparison of extreme surfaces at maximum (red) and minimum (gray). Dental age groups of all individuals and abbreviations of all fossil individuals are listed in Table 1

2.5 | Analyses

Patterns of shape variation were investigated by performing a principal component analysis (PCA) of the Procrustes shape variables. Mughareh el'Aliya and all early *H. sapiens* fossils were not used to calculate the PCAs shown and discussed in detail in the main text but were instead projected into the plots, following established procedure (see e.g., Bosman et al., 2020; Harvati et al., 2019; Mori et al., 2020; Röding et al., 2021). Shape changes occurring along each plotted principal component (PC) were illustrated as direct visualization of the vertices of each PC extreme. Dental age groups and species attribution were not part of the calculation of the PCA, which is independent of group membership, but were shown post facto in the form of convex hulls in the corresponding PCA plots. Convex hulls were

calculated around the extreme points of each defined group and contain no information about confidence intervals. In addition, log centroid size (CS) and PC1 were plotted against each other to visualize their allometric relationship and their correlation was tested via Pearson correlation test. Ontogenetic trends were further explored as illustrations of consecutive dental age group mean shapes and by computation of the common allometric component (CAC). The CAC is a scaled vector of slopes from a pooled regression calculated based on PC scores, which were corrected for their group-specific means based on size (Mitteroecker et al., 2004). The correlation between the main PCs and CAC was tested via Pearson correlation tests and CAC scores and log CS were plotted against each other to visualize their relationship. Overall shapes between individuals were compared based on Procrustes Distances

FIGURE 5 Maxillary shape principal component analysis with Mugharet el'Aliya and all early *H. sapiens* fossils projected into the plot, PC1 plotted against PC3. Symbols, colors, and abbreviations as in Figure 4 and Table 1

(PD) of the entire shape captured in the Procrustes superimposed vertex coordinates of the dataset (e.g., Harvati, 2009; Mori & Harvati, 2019). Summary statistics were performed for the sample mean, standard deviation (s.d.), minimum and maximum for CS, and for mean and s.d. for PD. Statistical tests were considered significant at $\alpha \leq 0.05$.

2.6 | Software

All steps of the measurement protocols and the following analyses were carried out in a combination of two different software environments. Avizo 9.2 Lite (Visualization Science Group) was used to create meshes and to obtain fixed landmarks. All other steps were carried out in R (R Developmental Core Team, 2020) by using freely available R packages, mainly geomorph (version 4.0.4; Adams et al., 2022), mesheR (version 0.4.200213; Schlager, 2020), Morpho (version 2.9; Schlager, 2017), Rvcg (version 0.20.2; Schlager, 2017), and shapes

(version 1.2.6; Dryden, 2021). For details about the R code used for the surface registration see corresponding section in the Supplementary Information. Graphics were created in R and processed in Adobe Illustrator CS5.

3 | RESULTS

As expected, size as measured by CS shows an overall trend of maxillary size increase from younger dental age groups to the adults (Figure 3; Tables S3, S4, S5). On average, all early *H. sapiens* and Neanderthal dental age groups show larger CS than comparable recent modern humans, with Neanderthals showing the largest adult CS values. Mugharet el'Aliya and Qafzeh 10 fall within the Neanderthal variation of their corresponding dental age group 4 and within dental age group 5 and adult variation of later *H. sapiens*, respectively. The only fossil subadult that clearly falls within the range of later *H. sapiens* variation of its dental age group 3 is the youngest Neanderthal, Pech de l'Azé.

FIGURE 6 Box-Whisker plots as illustration of the distribution of pairwise Procrustes distances (PD) to Mugharet el'Aliya per dental age group within the later *H. sapiens*, early *H. sapiens* and Neanderthal samples. PD of all individuals listed in Tables S2. Symbols, colors, and abbreviations as in Figure 3 and Table 1

A set of vertices resulting from surface registration was analyzed in two PCAs, one calculated based on the entire sample and one with Mugharet el'Aliya and all early *H. sapiens* fossils projected into the plots (cf. Section 2.5; Figures 4 and 5; Figure S4). Results of both PCAs were similar and therefore, only the results of the PCA in which Mugharet el'Aliya and all early *H. sapiens* fossils were projected into the plots are discussed below (cf. Figure 4 and Figure S4).

The first PC explains 60.15% of the total variance and summarizes shape changes related to width and height, as well as the relative position of the root of the zygomatic process in relation to the dentition. Individuals with positive PC1 scores show a relatively wide and low maxilla, with a rather anteriorly placed root of the zygomatic process. Individuals with negative PC1 scores show a relatively narrow and tall maxilla with a rather posteriorly placed root of the zygomatic process. These shape changes are highly negatively correlated with CS as well as dental age group (Figure S5) with Pearson correlation coefficients of -0.714 for shape summarized in PC1 and CS ($T = -9.008$, DoF = 78, $p < 0.01$) and of -0.834 for PC1 and dental age groups ($T = -13.315$, DoF = 78, $p < 0.01$). Thereby, PC1 separates partially consecutive age groups of Neanderthals, early and later

H. sapiens, as well as adult Neanderthals from the adult *H. sapiens* samples. All subadult fossils of both species, including Mugharet el'Aliya, plot within the PC1 variation of subadult later *H. sapiens* and, except for Pech de l'Azé, show CSs greater than the later *H. sapiens* maximum of their respective dental age groups (Figures 3 and 4; Tables S3, S4, S5).

PC2 and PC3 capture some interspecific and mostly intraspecific variation but are not significantly correlated to CS or dental age groups. PC2 explains 10.87% of the total variance and summarizes shape changes from an anteriorly oriented zygoma, concave anterior maxillary surface, and narrow nasal area (more positive PC2 scores); to a receding zygoma, relatively flat anterior maxillary surface, and wide nasal area leading to a medial displacement of the anterior dentition relative to the lateral border of the nasal apparatus (more negative PC2 scores). PC3 captures 6.32% of the total variance and summarizes shape changes from a maxilla with the anterior dentition being anterior to the lower part of the nasal apparatus and an arched IZM (more positive PC3 scores); to a maxilla with anterior dentition being on the same plane as the lower part of the nasal apparatus and relatively straight IZM (more negative PC3 scores).

FIGURE 7 Common allometric component (CAC) scores plotted against log CS. Symbols, colors, and abbreviations as in Figure 4 and Table 1

When combining PC1 and PC2, the maxillae from Mugharet el'Aliya and Qafzeh 10 plot into the convex hull of a younger later *H. sapiens* age group than their own dental status would suggest (Figure 4). In contrast, the subadult Neanderthals plot into the corresponding later *H. sapiens* convex hulls of their dental age groups. Neanderthal adults are fully separated from the adult *H. sapiens* samples by the combination of PC1 and PC2 as well as PC1 and PC3, while the adult early *H. sapiens* sample overlaps almost completely with the variation observed in later *H. sapiens* (Figures 4 and 5).

The Procrustes Distances (PD) calculated for the dataset show that Mugharet el'Aliya is most similar in its overall shape to the Qafzeh 10 individual (Figure 6; Table S2; cf. Figure 8). The Neanderthals closest in overall shape are Roc de Marsal and Pech de l'Azé which belong to a younger age group than Mugharet el'Aliya. The two Neanderthals of comparable dental age show a greater pairwise PD to Mugharet el'Aliya than almost all *H. sapiens* individuals from age groups 3 and 4, which is reflected in the mean pairwise PDs per dental age group (Figure 6; Table S2).

A CAC was calculated based on the previously obtained PC scores and plotted against log CS to further examine the allometric relationship of the PCs, especially PC1 (Figure 7). The CAC scores are highly negatively correlated with the PC1 scores with a Pearson

correlation coefficient of -0.952 ($T = -27.495$, $DoF = 78$, $p < 0.01$). The other PCs show no significant correlation with the CAC. The calculation based on scores from all PCs does not allow for direct visualization of the shape changes along the CAC but the high correlation with PC1 suggests similar shape changes (Figure S6). The CAC more clearly separates early and later *H. sapiens*, and Neanderthals when plotted against log CS compared to PC1 (cf. Figure 7 and Figure S5). These differences do not significantly affect the slopes of each group's ontogenetic allometric trend (Table S6), while the intercept with the x-axis, here log CS, between groups differs (cf. Figure 3; Table S5). Mugharet el'Aliya plots within the later *H. sapiens* variation for CAC versus log CS, while it plots outside the same variation and closer to the younger Neanderthal from Roc de Marsal in the case of PC1 versus log CS. Qafzeh 10 on the other hand plots in both cases closest to Roc de Marsal and outside the later *H. sapiens* variation.

Dental age group mean shapes calculated from the Procrustes coordinates of each individual for each group illustrate overall shape differences between groups as well as between consecutive age groups (Figure 8). For later *H. sapiens*, ontogenetic changes include increasing concavity of the anterior maxillary surface, a slight posterior shift of the relative position of the root of the zygomatic process in relation to the dentition, a slight increase in height relative to width, and until age group

FIGURE 8 Illustration of maxillary ontogenetic shape changes. Shapes shown as group mean shapes per dental age group. Direct comparison of surfaces from consecutive mean shapes with the younger dental age group in gray and the older in red. Dental age groups of all individuals listed in Table 1. Mugharet e'Aliya is courtesy of the Peabody Museum of Archaeology and Ethnology, Harvard University, 39-69-50/N3635.0.

5 a reduction of the alveolar prognathism; whereas the arched IZM and relative nasal width show little change. For early *H. sapiens*, the most prominent ontogenetic shape changes between the one subadult and the adult individuals in our sample include a widening of the nasal area, a posterior shift of the relative position of the root of the zygomatic process in relation to the dentition, a slight increase of the concavity of the anterior maxillary surface, and an increase in height relative to width; while the alveolar prognathism and arched IZM show little change. In contrast, the most prominent ontogenetic changes for Neanderthals include a pronounced increase in height relative to width particularly in the lateral aspect, a pronounced posterior shift of the relative position of the root of the zygomatic process in relation to the dentition, a slight widening of the nasal area, a pronounced widening of the arch at the IZM between age groups 3 and 4, and an increase in midfacial prognathism; while the concavity of the anterior maxillary surface shows little change. Thereby, early *H. sapiens* deviates in some respects from later *H. sapiens* but overall shows an ontogenetic trajectory more similar to later *H. sapiens* than to Neanderthals.

4 | DISCUSSION

4.1 | Maxillary morphology

The previous attribution of Mugharet el'Aliya to the Neanderthal lineage was based on its absolute size, particularly in the dentition, and on maxillary features such as the absence of a distinct canine fossa and a receding zygomatic arch (cf. Şenyürek, 1940). Our analysis confirmed the large overall size of this specimen in relation to our comparative sample (Figure 3; Tables S3, S4, S5). Its CS falls above the later *H. sapiens* variation of its own dental age group and within the range of the consecutive dental age group 5. All fossil subadults in our sample, with the exception of the youngest Neanderthal Pech de l'Azé, show a greater CS than the later *H. sapiens* of their respective dental age groups. Zollikofer et al. (2022) reported a similar result by showing that the viscerocranial size of fossil *H. sapiens* typically exceeds that of recent *H. sapiens* at any ontogenetic stage including adults. However, our analysis of maxillary morphology could not

clearly differentiate between early and later *H. sapiens* and Neanderthal subadults along the main shape PCs (Figures 4 and 5). Plotting the CAC against log CS showed less overlap between groups with this separation being mostly explained by a shift in size between early and later *H. sapiens* and Neanderthals (Figure 7; Table S6). The early *H. sapiens* sample follows this pattern by plotting closer to the similarly sized Neanderthals than relatively smaller later *H. sapiens*. Forbes Quarry overlaps with the later *H. sapiens* variation, which reflects its known small facial size (cf. Figure 3; Tables S3, S4; e.g., Trinkaus, 1984; references therein). In contrast, Mugharet el'Aliya deviates from this pattern and falls within later *H. sapiens* variation despite its large size (cf. Figures 3, 4, 7; Table S5). In addition, overall shape based on PD, age group mean shapes and the zygomatic root position showed affinities of the subadult Mugharet el'Aliya individual to our *H. sapiens* samples, especially to a subadult individual from Qafzeh, Israel (Figures 4, 6, 8; Table S2).

The state of preservation of Mugharet el'Aliya remains a major limiting factor to its analysis. For example, we could not fully evaluate its canine fossa morphology, as postmortem damage, both taphonomic and incurred during the extraction of the unerupted teeth, has resulted in considerable damage to this region. Moreover, the maxillary fragment is not preserved up to the midline, which is commonly used as a reference plane to define a receding zygoma. When comparing only the preserved morphology (cf. Measurement Protocol), adult Neanderthal facial characteristics include mid-facial prognathism, "inflated" morphology of the infra-orbital plate lacking a distinct canine fossa, receding zygomatic arches without an arched IZM and wide nasal apertures, as well as larger overall facial size (cf. Figures 3 and 8; Table S5; e.g., Bermúdez de Castro et al., 1997; Clement et al., 2012; Harvati, 2015; Harvati et al., 2010; Hublin, 1998; Trinkaus, 1987). Most of these traits are not exclusive to Neanderthals individually, but their combination helps define them as a distinct group (Clement et al., 2012; Harvati et al., 2010). Our data set successfully captured these features, as reflected in our PCA results which clearly separate adult Neanderthals from our adult *H. sapiens* samples on PC1-3 and PC2-3 (Figures 4 and 5). In contrast, no combination of the main PCs can separate the adult early *H. sapiens* sample from later *H. sapiens*, despite early *H. sapiens* on average showing more pronounced alveolar prognathism, a slightly more receding but still arched IZM (Figures 4, 5, 8). Only the greater maxillary size in early *H. sapiens* allows a separation within adult *H. sapiens* (Figures 3 and 7; Figure S5).

The distinct facial shapes of hominins are established in the early postnatal stages, that is, before the eruption of the first permanent molar, with relatively few changes in later ontogenetic stages (e.g., Ackermann & Krovitz, 2002; Bastir & Rosas, 2004; Cobb & O'Higgins, 2004). It must be noted that our subadult comparative samples of Neanderthals and especially early *H. sapiens* are limited and may not be representative. Nevertheless, our results indicate that marked maxillary shape changes continue into later postnatal stages in Neanderthals, while distinct facial characteristics of later *H. sapiens* are only accentuated (Figure 8). Mugharet el'Aliya and Qafzeh 10 seem to support the hypothesis that the later *H. sapiens* ontogenetic pattern

evolved rather recently (e.g., Williams, 2013). Despite their morphological similarities and comparable dental age, Mugharet el'Aliya shows a more developed shape than most similarly aged later *H. sapiens*, while the shape of Qafzeh 10 more closely resembles younger later *H. sapiens* individuals (cf. Figures 6 and 7).

Therefore, certain features should be treated with caution when evaluating the taxonomic status of fossil subadult maxillae. The absence of a deep, expanded, and distinct canine fossa and the presence of a slightly receding zygoma are shared between Mugharet el'Aliya and several subadult individuals, both *H. sapiens* and Neanderthal, especially those of comparable dental age to the Mugharet el'Aliya fossil (dental age group 4; cf. Figures 4 PC2, 8). After the eruption of the first permanent molar (age group 4), mid-facial prognathism and curvature of the IZM appear to differentiate early and later *H. sapiens* from Neanderthals (cf. Figures 5 PC3, 8). Neanderthals show an ontogenetic trend from slight alveolar prognathism and weak curvature at the IZM toward mid-facial prognathism and a rather straight IZM reflecting increased levels of remodeling and bone deposition in the nasal area during ontogeny, potentially leading to their adult mid-facial prognathism (Lacruz et al., 2015). In contrast, the majority of the *H. sapiens* samples shows alveolar prognathism and arched IZM with both features present during ontogeny, while in early *H. sapiens* the alveolar prognathism increases (cf. Figures 5 PC3, 8). Some Holocene subadult and adult modern humans from Central Europe lack clear alveolar prognathism and thereby show an anterior dentition almost on the same level as the lower part of the nasal opening (cf. Figure 5 PC3). The differences within our modern human sample might be linked to population-specific differences in the ontogenetic remodeling of the maxilla (Freidline et al., 2012; Schuh et al., 2020). It has been suggested that such differences in bone remodeling patterns are maintained throughout ontogeny in several *H. sapiens* populations (Schuh et al., 2020). The absence of a clear alveolar prognathism in Mugharet el'Aliya may reflect such differences in the remodeling of the maxilla. Our attempts to reveal the growth remodeling pattern in this fossil were unsuccessful due to its curation with a thick layer of preservative (cf. Section 2.3).

One aspect shared between ontogenetic trends in early and later *H. sapiens* as well as Neanderthals is a shift in the relative position of the root of the zygomatic process in relation to the dentition (Figure 4 PC1, Figures 7 and 8; Figure S6). With increasing age, the root of the zygomatic process moves to a more posterior position, with adult Neanderthals showing more posterior zygomatic root positions than our adult *H. sapiens* samples. A relatively posterior zygomatic root position is considered a Neanderthal derived feature (e.g., Trinkaus, 1987; Weber & Krenn, 2017). The Mugharet el'Aliya specimen shows a more anterior zygomatic root position, as expected for its dental age group (Minugh-Purvis, 1993). This is reflected by it plotting toward the younger dental age group 3 than its own dental age group 4 (Figure 4 PC1). In our sample, this tendency is shared with the subadult early *H. sapiens* individual Qafzeh 10, which is also closest in overall shape based on PD to Mugharet el'Aliya (Table S2). Additionally, some adult later *H. sapiens* individuals in our sample show relatively anterior placed zygomatic roots, including Nazlet Khater 2 (Egypt), for which this feature has been

described previously (Crevecoeur, 2012), and most distinctly a Holocene individual from Tanzania (Figure 4 PC1). In contrast, the subadult Neanderthals in our sample plot into their corresponding later *H. sapiens* dental age groups or even closer to the overlap with older age groups, and thereby mirror the adult condition of relatively more posterior zygomatic roots in Neanderthals.

4.2 | Placing Mugharet el'Aliya and the Aterian in a broader context

The initial description of Mugharet el'Aliya in 1940 and its attribution to the Neanderthal lineage were carried out in the context of a much more limited knowledge of the human fossil record. Today's understanding of human evolution and the relationship between modern humans and Neanderthals has been drastically reshaped by recent discoveries and methodological advances (e.g., Berger et al., 2010; Harvati et al., 2019; Hublin et al., 2017; Reich et al., 2010; Villanea & Schraiber, 2019). In this framework, the absolute dental and facial size, which were among the principal features used to group Mugharet el'Aliya with the Neanderthal lineage, are now known to be variable features and therefore are inadequate as sole phylogenetic indicators (e.g., Bernal et al., 2010). Megadonty, especially in mesio-distal dimensions, is associated with a relative size increase of the corresponding jaw. In contrast, particularly in recent *H. sapiens* jaw and facial size might be reduced due to the potential absence of wisdom teeth (Oeschger et al., 2020).

Nevertheless, the factors potentially underlying such great robustness and megadonty in Aterian populations, that may be as recent as 20 ka before present (Doerschner et al., 2016; Richter et al., 2012), should be investigated. Other studies of the Aterian fossil record have reported a mosaic of derived modern and ancestral traits, including general robusticity and relatively large size, shared with Middle Pleistocene African fossils (Ferembach, 1976; Hublin, 2000; Hublin et al., 2012; Hublin & Tillier, 1981). The rather clear shape affiliation of Aterian fossils with *H. sapiens* combined with archaic traits such as large size might indicate previous hybridization with surviving archaic lineages or reflect retention of ancestral traits (Ackermann, 2011). The overall maxillary dental pattern of Aterian fossils from the Témara region showed similarities to Peștera cu Oase 2, Romania (Hublin et al., 2012). Hybridization between modern humans and Neanderthals was suggested for the individuals from Oase and could be confirmed by paleogenetic analyses (Fu et al., 2015; Rougier et al., 2007; Siska, 2019; Trinkaus et al., 2013). Evidence from genetics indicates not only admixture between modern humans and Neanderthals, but also suggests introgression from ghost populations into the modern human African gene pool (e.g., Durvasula & Sankararaman, 2020; Hsieh et al., 2016; Lachance et al., 2012). Additionally, the unusually large size of admixed individuals is a commonly described effect of hybridization (e.g., Ackermann, 2011; Harvati, 2009; Harvati & Roksandic, 2016). However, this hypothesis cannot be tested for the Aterian without further genetic evidence and additional fossils providing a more complete picture of the morphological variation associated with the Aterian.

Recent re-evaluation of the Aterian fossil record supports the hypothesis of retained archaic traits due to regional continuity, which would be in accordance with a re-evaluation of dates and lithic assemblages associated with the Aterian. Historically, the Aterian was dated to 40–20 ka based on radiocarbon dates (Debénath, 2000; Wengler, 1997). Employing additional dating methods including ESR or Uranium/Thorium pushed back the beginning of the Aterian to MIS6 around 145 ka (Barton et al., 2009; Richter et al., 2010). The Aterian apparently overlaps with an early MSA industry by up to 85 ka in the region of today's Morocco and Algeria (Dibble et al., 2013). Several sites show Aterian layers below layers with supposedly earlier MSA assemblages in a stratified context (Aouadi-Abdeljaouad & Belhouchet, 2008; Nami & Moser, 2010; Richter et al., 2010). Thereby, a distinction of the Northwest African MSA into multiple industries has been questioned (Linstädter et al., 2012; Richter et al., 2012; Scerri, 2017; Scerri & Spinapolica, 2019). The Aterian was often recognized by the presence of the so-called “tanged” pieces. Although additional characteristics were identified, some researchers claim that the similarities between the industries are too great to separate them (Dibble et al., 2013; Richter et al., 2012; Scerri, 2017). This would suggest a degree of regional continuity within North African MSA industries. A similar hypothesis of a regional continuity was proposed for the Northwest African MSA associated hominin fossil record (Bergmann et al., 2022; Hublin, 2000; Hublin et al., 2017; Nespoulet et al., 2008). The hominin fossils from the late Middle Pleistocene and Late Pleistocene associated with Northwest African MSA technology show anatomical similarities, whereas later populations in the region associated with the LSA seem to differ morphologically (Harvati & Hublin, 2012; Hublin, 2000; Hublin et al., 2017; Nespoulet et al., 2008; Scerri, 2017). However, recent re-evaluation of mandibular morphology suggests an extension of the regional continuity into both the LSA and the Middle Pleistocene by linking MSA individuals from Jebel Irhoud and the Aterian to an LSA sample of Iberomaurusians and late Early/Middle Pleistocene individuals, respectively (Bergmann et al., 2022). In addition to similar mandibular morphologies, individuals from Jebel Irhoud and the Aterian show a comparable combination of the same primitive retentions, including large overall size and megadonty, and modern features as well as similarities with the samples from Qafzeh and Skhul (Ferembach, 1976; Freidline et al., 2021; Harvati & Hublin, 2012; Hublin et al., 2012; Hublin et al., 2017; Hublin & Tillier, 1981; Hublin & Tillier, 1988). Large facial and dental size relative to recent *H. sapiens* are frequent traits in many late Middle and early Late Pleistocene African fossils, for example, Herto, Rabat-Kébibat, Kabwe, and some individuals from Haua Fteah and Klasies River Mouth (e.g., Bräuer, 2012; Hublin et al., 2012; Hublin et al., 2017; McBurney et al., 1953; Oujaa et al., 2017; Rightmire & Deacon, 1991; White et al., 2003). In contrast, in the second half of the Late Pleistocene such extremes are rare outside the northwestern African fossil record due to facial reduction in *H. sapiens* (e.g., Bastir & Rosas, 2016; Lieberman et al., 2002; Trinkaus, 2003).

However, the majority of human fossils associated with the Aterian and earlier Northwest African MSA have been found in

Morocco, often along the Atlantic coast (Freidline et al., 2021; Hublin et al., 2012). These fossils span a long period, from ca. 300 ka represented by Jebel Irhoud, to potentially as recent as 35 ka as represented by Mugharet el'Aliya (Hublin et al., 2017; Richter et al., 2017; Wrinn & Rink, 2003). Dating of archeological sites roughly coincides with wet periods in MIS5 for both lithic industries and MIS3 for the Aterian in today's Sahara, Morocco, and Algeria whereas the gaps in the fossil record seem to reflect dry periods in MIS4 (Drake & Breeze, 2016; Jacobs et al., 2012). Wet periods were characterized by megalakes and river channels in today's Sahara Desert (Armitage et al., 2007; Osborne et al., 2008) and thereby, presenting a scenario of connected Aterian sites across North Africa from the Moroccan Atlantic coast to the Nile valley. Nevertheless, the known morphology and dated lithic assemblages within the Aterian are snapshots, which complicates their comparison with the earlier Northwest African MSA and other sites associated with early *H. sapiens*. Comparing Mugharet el'Aliya with earlier MSA subadult fossil maxillae such as the Contrebandiers fossil (Balter, 2011; Freidline et al., 2021; Jacobs et al., 2011) would be relevant to address questions on the hypothesis of regional continuity throughout the Moroccan MSA.

4.3 | Methodological considerations

The Aterian fossil record is partially unpublished or poorly described (cf. Hublin et al., 2012). The lack of suitable methods available at the time of their discovery and the fragmented nature of the fossil remains may have contributed to their limited exposure in human evolution research. The surface registration method implemented here has the potential to be a robust research alternative to analyze fragmentary specimens, common in the fossil record, that do not preserve enough linear measurements or homologous landmarks for a conventional linear analysis or typical geometric morphometric study. It can potentially enable the investigation of the entire preserved morphology of specimens that were hitherto impossible to analyze quantitatively. To our knowledge, the present study is among the first to use surface registration in an archeological context.

The process of surface registration is sensitive to missing data, and the measurement protocol described here necessitates the exclusion of all individuals with large areas of missing data or missing data in crucial parts of the surface of interest. Only individuals with relatively small locally confined damage, that is, cracks, porosities, or additional foramen, can still be included. In these cases, the matched surface can differ locally more than 1 mm from the original and is smoothed during the ICP-matching (Figure S3d–f). Furthermore, the amount of data produced by the surface registration method can be enormous. The geometric complexity of the anatomical structure under study determines the mesh resolution and, in turn, the number of vertices and variables used during analyses. On the one hand, in complex geometric structures a reduction in mesh resolution might lead to systematic artifacts during the ICP-matching (Figure S7). On the other hand, a high mesh resolution can render the calculation of

some commonly used analyses almost impossible, for example, in our data set the calculation of a canonical variate analysis based on Procrustes coordinates would require an integer that lays beyond the codomain supported by R. Further research is needed to adjust the method of surface registration to the field of paleoanthropology, for example in combination with data reduction techniques and statistical shape models, which are already used for reconstruction of damaged skeletal areas in computer-assisted surgery (e.g., Semper-Hogg et al., 2017).

5 | CONCLUSIONS

Mugharet el'Aliya adds to the growing number of subadult hominins recovered from sites across Africa enabling a better understanding of facial ontogeny in the fossil record. Yet, the fragmentary nature of the maxilla highlights the necessity to develop new analytical tools to study incomplete specimens. Surface registration allowed the placement of this fossil in a quantitative comparative framework based on most of its surviving external morphology. Based on our results, we conclude that the preserved facial anatomy of the juvenile fossil from Mugharet el'Aliya more closely aligns with that of Late Pleistocene *H. sapiens* individuals and we found no clear affinities to the Neanderthal lineage. Previous associations of this specimen with the Neanderthal lineage were likely due to its large absolute size and to features such as its shallow canine fossa, which are ontogenetically variable among modern humans, and therefore not necessarily informative on phylogenetic relationships. Whether these observed features are primitive retentions or may reflect admixture between early *H. sapiens* and archaic lineages is unclear.

The similarities between Mugharet el'Aliya and an early *H. sapiens* individual from the Levant add to the evidence connecting fossils from western Asia, especially Qafzeh and Skhul, and the North African Late Pleistocene human fossil record (see e.g., Freidline et al., 2021; Harvati & Hublin, 2012; Shea & Bar-Yosef, 2005). The extent and phylogenetic relevance of such similarities, and the implications on possible connections across populations dated from ~300 ka to ca. 20 ka from the Moroccan Atlantic Coast to the Levant, remains an important area of research in human evolution.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

Carolyn Röding: Conceptualization (supporting); data curation (lead); formal analysis (lead); investigation (lead); methodology (lead); project administration (supporting); software (lead); validation (equal); visualization (lead); writing – original draft (lead); writing – review and editing (equal). **Chris Stringer:** Conceptualization (equal); funding acquisition (supporting); project administration (equal); resources (supporting); writing – review and editing (equal). **Rodrigo S. Lacruz:** Conceptualization (lead); funding acquisition (supporting); project administration (equal); resources (supporting); writing – review and editing (equal). **Katerina Harvati:** Conceptualization (lead); funding acquisition (lead); project administration (lead); resources (lead); supervision (lead); writing – review and editing (equal).

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

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